

Inclusion Strategies Used by the Jakarta Post to Represent Indonesia Government due to Policies against Pandemic

Imas Nita Juwita¹, Elvi Citraresmana², Sutiono Mahdi³
^{1, 2, 3}(Faculty of Cultural Sciences Universitas Padjadjaran)

ABSTRACT: *This research discusses how Inclusion Strategies used by the Jakarta Post to represent Indonesian government due to policies against pandemic. The form of data are sentences that are classified and analyzed that have inclusion strategies in the economic articles published by The Jakarta Post online news article from June to August 2020. The aim of this research is to show the inclusion strategies used by the Jakarta Post to represent Indonesian government, how Indonesian Government policies due to Pandemic to prevent Indonesia from the economic crisis. The analysis of this research was done by using qualitative and descriptive research methods. The use of inclusion strategies frequently showed in the news related to the recession issue. Researcher revealed that Indonesian government is mostly represented by using categorization-functionalization strategy, which are realized by using the actor's highest positions or jobs in the country. Therefore, The Jakarta Post represent Indonesian government as the actor that is really concerned towards the recession issue that the policies against pandemic which was decided by the Indonesian Government have an objective to minimize the pandemic effect such as economic crisis or recession.*

KEYWORDS - *Inclusion strategies, Representation, economic, pandemic*

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic issue has received serious attention Before COVID-19 first identified positive in Indonesia, Jokowi took a policy to increase the massive growth of infrastructure rapidly to achieve economic growth. However, since COVID-19 attack any country including Indonesia, this becomes a new chapter that has the impact of economic growth in any countries including Indonesia. Every policy which has taken by The Government related to coronavirus pandemic as problem solving strategy has affected economic condition for poor categories, middle categories even for rich categories of society.

The writer learned from some related study. Previous research was conducted by Eri Kurniawan and Amalia Dwi Utami (2017) entitled "The Representation of Joko Widodo's Figure in Jakarta Post". The analysis was done by using nomination and predication strategies of Discourse Historical Approach (DHA) submitted by Reisigl and Wodak (2001) to reveal deixis and synecdoche. The next study was conducted by Rosaria Mita Amalia (2009) entitled "Representasi Pemerintah Indonesia dalam Pemberitaan Kasus Ambalat antara Indonesia dan Malaysia". This study presents a total explanation of Indonesian representation on Ambalat event between Indonesia and Malaysia as indicate in a news article which was published by 'Kompas online'. This study uses the theory from Van Dijk. The result of this study is representation of Indonesian Government that showed in the news article tend to positive.

After elaborated initial understanding from previous paper, the researcher continues to construct this paper. This study examines The Jakarta Post online news article as it is well known for common Indonesian people and so popular in Indonesia. The writer applies theory by van Leeuwen (2008) in this research that was popular with his social actor representation concept. As discussed in this research the trend of local news media

has representation on how they inform public Indonesian Government's strategy to maintain Indonesian economic during pandemic condition.

The media has the capability to create the people's opinion so they would have the same idea with the text producer. As an institution nowadays press has media power where "Freedom of Press" was known as "power of press" based on van Dijk (1995). Mind control had been presupposed by control of action as the main of persuasive social power. Then a cognitive science which has social intention present point of view into these ways and structures of cognition, therefore it provides an option a basic of new standard of persuasive power of the media (Graber 1984; Gunter 1987; Harris 1989; van Dijk 1988). Hence, it offers them an extraordinary power and control to deliver the news (phenomenon) or to construct partial description of the actors involved based on their interest and each own point of view. By using this concept, the writer can observe how the news maker affect public when they release an article by their focus where they have packaged the news on their article.

So, this concept is fit to test the data compared with others. Finally, all the rationale above pushes the researcher to examine the representation of social actor implicated in the case of Indonesian Government's strategy to maintain Indonesian's economic development during COVID-19 pandemic condition, including the same idea how to deliver the news (pro) or the opposite idea how to deliver the news (contradict) that is published by Indonesian local media The Jakarta Post. The objective of the research is to know how the way Indonesian Government was represented through inclusion strategies.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study examines The Jakarta Post's articles pertaining Indonesian economic impact due to the policy during the pandemic period. There are 11 articles analyzed. This study is qualitative since this study focuses on answering questions descriptively, as proposed by Nassaji (2015). Nassaji explains both concepts that are qualitative and descriptive have been too mainstream techniques to arrange study in any subject, as well as education, linguistics, and social sciences. The objective of descriptive research is to show a phenomenon and its characteristics. The followings are the steps to analyze the data: first, the writers categorize the data based on van Leeuwen (2008) Social Actor Representation theory (inclusion); second, The writers use the theory the theory of lexical analysis: the choice of meaning of words from Richardson (2007) to help Analyzing the lexical choice of every data (inclusion); third, Illustrating how the text producers represent the Indonesian government and also show the text producers' aim to do particular representation based on the analysis of inclusion strategy and lexical analysis.

III. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data in all the articles, the writers classified there are several kinds of inclusion strategies that are used by The Jakarta Post when representation the Indonesian government. Some of the inclusion strategies can be described as follows:

1. Personalization

Data 1: **We** have asked ministries that if their budget cannot be absorbed fully, they should shift [the money] to programs that support productivity." TJP_26_08_20B

Data 2: "We must expedite the process so that spending can increase by the end of the third quarter and can be completed by the fourth quarter," **he** said. TJP_7_08_20

Data 3: "The budget absorption must be pushed continuously so that the economy can get on a positive track," **he** told reporters. TJP_26_08_20B

The data is categorized as personalization strategy since the text producer uses the pronoun 'he' to realize the actor. It is line with Van Leeuwen (2008) who states that this strategy can be realized by personal/possessive pronouns, proper names, or noun/adjectives which can be categorized to human features. Beside that these data are categorized as personalization since the verbs 'asked' and 'said' can only be done by

human. in addition, to emphasize the request The Jakarta Post also uses the modal verb ‘*should*’ means ‘*used for expressing strong agreement*’ (Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, n.d), and ‘*must*’ means ‘*used to say that something is necessary or very important*’ (Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, n.d). Therefore, from the lexical definition above, we can see the Jakarta post tries to highlight that Indonesia government really serious against economic restoration and growth.

2. Categorization-functionalization category

Van Leeuwen (2008) explain that strategy inclusion especially categorization in types of functionalization is the representation of social actors which referred to their activity or something they do. In this data, Indonesian government represented as activated social actor by the verb phrase ‘*aims to push*’, ‘*expects*’, and ‘*expressed*’, ‘*instructs*’.

Data 4: **President Joko “Jokowi” Widodo aims to push** the country’s economic recovery and structural reform amid the coronavirus-induced downturn in its proposed 2021 state budget draft. TJP_14_08_20B

Data 5: **The government expects** the economy to contract 0.4 percent this year, or to grow 1 percent at best. TJP_14_08_20B

Data 6: **The President** expressed hope for spending to occur between July and September to prevent a recession in the third quarter. TJP_13_08_20

Data 7: **President Joko “Jokowi” Widodo** has called on local administrations to accelerate their regional budget spending to help boost the economy after Indonesia’s gross domestic product (GDP) contracted in the second quarter. TJP_13_08_20

Data 8: **The President** always instructs us to disburse the economic recovery budget immediately so that the economy can recover sooner in the third quarter,” TJP_7_08_20

All data above are categorized as categorization –functionalization category since all the data above are used term which refers to particular roles or jobs. Such as the term ‘*President*’ means ‘*the leader of a republic*’ (Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, n.d), and the term ‘*government*’ means ‘*the group of people who are responsible for controlling a country or a state*’ (Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, n.d). The definition above refers to the job or the activity. The function of this strategy is to give impact to the news. By using the social actor’s activity or job, The Jakarta Post wants to show that the existence of social actors in the data do not only show his/her efforts to economic recovery amid the coronavirus-induced downturn, but also to show the seriousness of the actor since the actor is categorized as the most important positions in the country.

3. Role allocation

Data 9: **President** asked **all regional heads** to work harder to manage the health crisis and find a balance between the economy and public health. TJP_22_07_20B

The data above are categorized as activation –passivation strategies. Related to lexical analysis, the data above uses the verb ‘*asked*’ to activate the Indonesian government (the president and Indonesia) and passivate all regional heads at the same time. The verb ‘*asked*’ means ‘*to tell somebody that you would like them to do something or that you would like something to happen*’ (Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, n.d). Therefore, The Jakarta Post represented Indonesia government as the party who care to manage the health crisis and find a balance between the economy and public health with asked all regional heads to work harder.

4. Specification

Data 10: **Jokowi changes** 2020 state budget again, with deficit at 6.34% of GDP. TJP_26_06_20A

Data 11: **Jokowi sets sights** on economic recovery, structural reform in 2021 state budget. TJP_13_08_20

Data 12: **Sri Mulyani** expects the economy to grow at no more than 0.5 percent, or even contract further in the third quarter, while fourth-quarter GDP growth is projected to be near 3 percent, making for a full-year expansion of zero to 1 percent. TJP_7_08_20

Related to the data above, the proper name 'Jokowi' and 'Sri mulyani' is categorized as individualized social actor since the proper name 'Jokowi' refers to his position as the President of Republic of Indonesia, and proper name 'Sri Mulyani' refers to her position as Finance Minister of Indonesia that represents a group of actor i.e Indonesian government. It is in line with Van Leeuwen (2008) who states that specification in type of individualization occurs when the social actor is presented as individuals. The Jakarta Post chooses to use the verb 'change' and 'set sight' 'expects'. To emphasize the Indonesian government effort, the word 'change' mean 'to become different' (Oxford Learner's Dictionary, n.d), and the verb 'set' is defined as 'set something to arrange or fix something; to decide on something'(Oxford Learner's Dictionary, n.d). Therefore, the data can be interpreted that The Jakarta Post wants to emphasize that the actor Jokowi was trying to do the best against economic crisis due to pandemic.

5. Association

Data 13: Jokowi has instructed **Coordinating Maritime Affairs and Investment Minister Luhut Pandjaitan** to bolster investment in the third quarter this year, saying this, aside from boosting household spending, would be the key to economic growth. (TJP_26_08_20B).

Data 14: He said on Monday that **the ministries and government institutions** lacked a sense of urgency amid the health crisis. TJP_6_08_20

According Van Leeuwen (2008) explain that associations refer to groups formed by social actors and/or groups of social actors which are never labelled in the text. In this data, the text producer uses the association strategy which is realized by the proper names 'Coordinating Maritime Affairs and Investment Minister Luhut Pandjaitan' and 'the ministries and government institutions' instead of using 'Indonesian government'. This realization is done for specific function. He writer assumes that the text producer mentions the name and the position to affirm that the responsibilities of economic growing in Indonesia then set a job was not a wild person and was believed in helping economic growing commonly by escalating investment in Indonesia. Therefore, the way that the text producer represents the social actors can be indirectly directed to Indonesian government that is represented as the government that pays serious attention towards the escalating investment could be the key as a solution of economic growing.

6. Objectivation

According to van Leeuwen (2008), objectivation-spatialization is a form of objectivation in which the social actors are represented by means of reference to a place with which they are engaged.

Data 15: **Indonesia** has been implementing a partial lockdown, locally known as large-scale social restrictions (PSBB), in several regions. TJP_22_07_20B

Data 16: **The country** has achieved little in its fight against the pandemic. TJP_22_07_20A

The word 'Indonesia' and 'country' refers to the name of place. In this data, the word 'Indonesia' and 'the country' substitutes 'Indonesia government'. According to Van Leeuwen (2008) one of the functions of objectivation in type of spatialization is to background the identity and/or role of social actors. The word 'Indonesia' and 'country' to represent the Indonesia government is categorized as objectivation in type of spatialization category which has a function to background the role of the actor. According to online Oxford Learner's Dictionary the verb 'implementing' is defined 'to make something that has been officially decided start to happen or be used' and the verb 'achieve' which means 'achieve something to succeed in reaching a particular goal'. Therefore, the data above show that Indonesian government is represented as the party who have a control to a manage a strategy against pandemic.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examines the Inclusion strategies used by The Jakarta Post in the representation of the Indonesian government involved in the case. The use of inclusion strategies frequently showed in news due to the recession issue as an impact of the pandemic. The inclusion strategies used by The Jakarta Post are Personalization, Specification, Association, Categorization, and Objectivation. Through the strategy inclusion, The Jakarta Post to represent Indonesian government as the actor that is really concerned towards the recession issue that the policies against pandemic which was decided by the Indonesian Government have an objective to minimize the pandemic effect such as economic crisis or recession. The Jakarta Post mostly use the sociological category to represent Indonesian government, in the sociological category The Jakarta Post mostly uses specification strategy to represent Indonesia government yang make all decision related to economy recovery in the representation. In addition, this study revealed that the Indonesian government is mostly represented by using a categorization-functionalization strategy which is realized by using the actor's highest positions or jobs in the country. such as 'Indonesian President', 'Coordinating Maritime Affairs and Investment Minister', 'Coordinating Economic Minister', 'the government' etc. Therefore, it indicates that The Jakarta Post represents the Indonesian government as the actor that is really concerned about the issue.

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